

Chemical Investigation of *Boucerosia aucheriana* Doné: Isolation of Dibehenate of 1,26-Hexacosane Diol.

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From the aerial parts of *Boucerosia aucheriana*, 1,26-hexacosanediol, $C_{26}H_{54}O_2$, a new wax designated as boucerosin, $C_{70}H_{138}O_4$ and a saponin have been isolated. On hydrolysis, boucerosin furnishes behenic acid, $C_{22}H_{44}O_2$ and 1,26-hexacosanediol.

Boucerosia aucheriana' (Fam. Asclepiadaceae) is a small fleshy herb which grows in the dry hills of Western Punjab, Waziristan and Beluchistan. The stems of the plant are used in various ailments e.g. as stomachic, carminative, febrifuge and bitter tonic.

A chemical investigation of the aerial parts of the plant in this laboratory has resulted in the isolation of (i) an alcohol, (ii) a wax and (iii) a saponin, the first two from the extract of petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) and the third from chloroform extract of the plant. Petroleum ether extract on concentration deposits a white solid. The latter on chromatographic resolution over Brockmann alumina using petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) and chloroform respectively as eluents yields the wax and the alcohol. The saponin separates out from the concentrated chloroform extract by treatment with ether.

From elemental analysis and molecular weight determination, the composition of the alcohol has been established as $C_{26}H_{54}O_2$ (M.W. 401, Rast method). It needs mention in this connection that the molecular weight of alcohol could not be determined by mass spectrometry as the sample is nonvolatile in the inlet tube. The alcohol, m.p. 110° (yield 0.05%) contains at least one OH group, indicated by its I.R. spectrum (absorption at 2.9μ). It does not give Liebermann-Bürchard test for sterol or triterpene and also tetranitromethane test for unsaturation. It does not contain any C-CH₃ or O-CH₃ group, but has two active hydrogen atoms, which are associated with two hydroxyls as the compound forms a diacetate, $C_{30}H_{58}O_4$, m.p. 75°. From an examination of its elemental analysis, physical and chemical properties, the alcohol appeared to be identical with 1,26-hexacosane diol¹. This was confirmed by mixed melting point determination and I.R. spectra comparison with an authentic sample of the diol.

The wax, boucerosin, $C_{70}H_{138}O_4$ (M.W. 1042), m.p. 89°, (yield, 0.1%) contains two C-CH₃ but no O-CH₃ group. Infrared spectrum of the compound indicates the presence of a carbonyl function (5.8μ) proved to be an ester carbonyl, as on hydrolysis with 10% alcoholic KOH it gives an alcohol and an acid. Elemental analysis and melting point of the alcohol ($C_{26}H_{54}O_2$, m.p. 110°) suggest that it is identical with its congener, 1,26-hexacosane diol (*vide supra*) which has been confirmed by mixed melting point determination and superim-

1. Kirtikar and Basu, "Indian Medicinal Plants", Part II, p. 834. 1918; Chopra, Nayer and Chopra, "Glossary of Indian Medicinal Plants, C. S. I. R. (India) 1956, p. 40.
2. Murray and Schoenfeld, *Aust. J. Chem.* 1955, 8, 432.

possible infrared spectra. The acid, $C_{21}H_{44}O_2$, m.p. 77° forms an ester, $C_{21}H_{43}CO_2CH_3$, m.p. 52° with diazomethane. The methyl ester shows a molecular ion peak at m/e 354. It does not produce any yellow colouration with tetranitromethane indicating the absence of unsaturation in the acid which is also proved from its molecular formula. Infrared spectrum of the acid contains only a carbonyl absorption at 5.9μ . NMR spectrum of the methyl ester of the acid shows a (3H) signal at 0.8 τ for a $-CH_3$ group, a large (38H) signal at 1.25 τ for $-CH_2-$ groups, a (2H) signal at 2.2 τ for the $-CH_2-$ adjacent to carbomethoxy group and a (3H) signal at 3.6 τ for $-COOCH_3$ group. These chemical and physical evidences establish the identity of the acid as helenic acid which was further substantiated by mixed melting point determination and superimposable I. R. spectra. Consequently boucerosin is the dibenzoate of 1,26-hexacosane diol.

The saponin, which has been obtained as a reddish-yellow powder by repeated precipitation from chloroform solution with ether, decomposes at $210-20^\circ$. It produces a single spot (R_f 0.93) when subjected to paper chromatography using n -butanol-acetic acid-water (4:1:5) as solvent and trichloroacetic acid as indicator. It has been proved to contain D-glucose residues by hydrolysis with H_2SO_4 and paper chromatography³ of the hydrolysate with n -butanol-ethanol-water (45:5:50) as solvent and ammoniacal silver nitrate as indicator when a single spot is obtained. The R_f value (0.105) suggests the presence of D-glucose in the hydrolysate which has been confirmed by running a parallel chromatogram with an authentic sample of D-glucose. The genin obtained as a brown powder from the hydrolysis of the saponin, decomposes at $110-20^\circ$ and gives a green colouration in Liebermann-Burchard test. Further work on the genin is in progress.

EXPERIMENTAL

Isolation of 1,26-Hexacosanediol and the Wax.—Air-dried and powdered stems of *Boucerosia aucheriana* (1 kg.) were extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus with petroleum ether (b.p. $60-80^\circ$) for 48 hr. The extract was concentrated and cooled when a solid separated. The solid, m.p. $80-82^\circ$, was filtered and washed repeatedly with ether (yield, 4 g). It was dissolved in least quantity of chloroform, adsorbed on Brockmann alumina and eluted with solvents in order of increasing polarity, starting with petroleum ether (b.p. $60-80^\circ$). The wax (A) was washed down from the column by petroleum ether (b.p. $60-80^\circ$) and the diol by chloroform.

The wax (A) was repeatedly crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. $60-80^\circ$) till there was no further rise in melting point. The pure sample melted at 87° (yield, 1 g). (Found: C, 80.56; H, 13.65; O, 5.89, $C-CH_3$, 2.40. $C_{70}H_{138}O_4$ requires: C, 80.61; H, 13.24; O, 6.14; 2 $C-CH_3$, 2.87%.

The diol was crystallised from chloroform followed by benzene-acetone mixture. It melted at 110° (yield, 0.5 g). The melting point remained undepressed when admixed with an authentic sample of 1,26-hexacosanediol. The I. R. spectra of the two compounds were also superimposable. (Found: C, 78.09; H, 13.36; $C-CH_3$, 0.95; H^+ , 0.55%. Calc. for $C_{26}H_{54}O_2$: C, 78.39; H, 13.57; 1- $C-CH_3$, 3.79; 2 H^+ , 0.50%, M.W. 398).

Acetylation of 1,26-Hexacosnediol. A mixture of the diol (0.3 g) and acetic anhydride (5 ml) was heated in a sealed tube at 170° in an oil-bath for 4 hr. The tube was cooled, opened and the contents poured over crushed ice with stirring. The mixture was allowed to stand for several hrs. and the solid acetate filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from acetone. It melted at 75-76° (yield, 0.25 g). (Found: -COCH₃, 17.48. Calc. for 2 -COCH₃, 17.44%).

Saponification of the Wax (A). The wax (1 g) was refluxed with alcoholic KOH (25 ml, 10%) on water-bath for 16 hr. Alcohol was removed by evaporation on water-bath, residue treated with water and filtered. The filtrate which did not contain any potassium salt of organic acid was rejected. The residue was washed with water, dried and extracted repeatedly with warm chloroform. The chloroform extract was concentrated and cooled when a solid separated which was crystallised from benzene-acetone mixture. It melted at 110° (yield, 0.4 g). (Found: C, 78.64; H, 13.33. Calc. for C₂₆H₅₄O₂: C, 78.39; H, 13.37%). Melting point of the compound remained undepressed when admixed with 1,26-hexacosnediol.

The residue left after extraction with chloroform contained potassium salt of the organic acid of the ester. The salt was heated on water-bath with glacial acetic acid till a clear solution was obtained. The solution was poured into a large volume of water and the solid acid which separated was filtered. The filtrate was rejected and the residue was washed with water, dried and taken in ether which on evaporation gave a pale yellow residue. It was crystallised from petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°), m.p. 77° (yield, 0.4 g). (Found: C, 77.25; H, 12.82. Calc. for C₂₆H₅₄O₂: C, 77.64; H, 12.93%).

Esterification of the Acid with Diazomethane.—An ethereal solution of the acid (0.1 g) was kept in an ice-bath and treated with diazomethane dissolved in the same solvent. The mixture was allowed to stand overnight, ether removed and the residue purified by chromatography over Brockmann alumina, petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) being used as the eluent. The ester melted at 52°. (Found: C, 78.23; H, 12.96; OCH₃, 8.89. Calc. for C₂₇H₅₆O₂: C, 77.96; H, 12.99; OCH₃, 8.76%).

Isolation of the Saponin—Dried and powdered stems of *B. aucheriana* (1 kg.), pre-treated with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°), were Soxhletted with chloroform for 48 hr. The extract was reduced to a small bulk, cooled and treated with ether till there was no further precipitation. The precipitate was filtered, dissolved in chloroform and reprecipitated with ether when a yellowish white powder, m.p. 210-20° (decom.) was obtained (yield, 15 g).

An aqueous solution of saponin was applied on Whatman no. 1 filter paper. The chromatogram was developed for 4 hr. in *n*-butanol-acetic acid-water (4:1:5, upper layer), using ascending technique. It was then dried in air, sprayed with 25% trichloroacetic acid in ether and dried at 120° for 5 min. when a single spot was obtained; R_f 0.93.

Hydrolysis of the Saponin.—A solution of the saponin (1 g) in water was heated on water-bath with excess of 4N sulphuric acid for 20 hr. The genin (0.6 g) was separated from the hydrolysate by filtration.

The genin (brown powder), m.p. 110-20° (decom.), could not be crystallised from common solvents. On chromatography over Brockmann or acid-washed alumina it was firmly adsorbed on the column.

The saponin hydrolysate after separation of the genin was neutralised with barium carbonate. The precipitated barium sulphate and the excess of barium carbonate were removed by filtration and the residue was washed with hot water. The combined filtrate and the washings were concentrated on water-bath under reduced pressure and chromatographed on Whatman no. 1 filter paper. The chromatogram was developed for 8 hr. in n-butanol-ethanol-water (45:5:50, upper layer) using ascending technique. It was dried in air, sprayed with ammoniacal silver nitrate solution and heated at 105° for 5 min. when a single spot was obtained. R_f value (0.105) indicated the presence of D-glucose in the hydrolysate. This was confirmed by running two parallel chromatograms with D-glucose and saponin hydrolysate respectively, when identical R_f values were obtained. The identity was further established by co-chromatogram.

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